

STUDIES IN CARBOHYDRATES. PART IV. INVESTIGATION OF MODAL GUM (*LANNEA GRANDIS*). STRUCTURE OF THE ALDOBIONIC ACID

BY V. M. PARIKH, T. R. INGLE AND B. V. BHIDE

The structure assigned to the aldobionic acid obtained from Modal gum (*Lannea grandis*) as 4-methyl-1:6-glucuronosido-galactose has been confirmed by preparing the amide (V) of its fully methylated derivative (III).

In Part III (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 119) it was shown that modal gum gave on hydrolysis an aldobionic acid consisting of one galactose and one methylglucuronic acid unit. A considerable decomposition was, however, observed during the hydrolysis with 10% H_2SO_4 , thus resulting in poor yields of aldobionic acid. Hydrolysis with 3% H_2SO_4 afforded a mixture of barium salts of uronic acids. The mixture had Ba, 13.3% and $\alpha_D^{25} \pm 0^\circ$. Barium salt of monouronic acid requires Ba, 26.2%, that of aldobionic acid, 15.66% and of aldotrionic acid, 11.2%. This mixture of the barium salts was subjected to further study.

Methylation of the barium salts of the acids, first with dimethyl sulphate and sodium hydroxide and finally with Purdie's reagent, furnished a product which on distillation under reduced pressure afforded two fractions, A and B. Fraction A was found to be methyl ester of 2:3:4-trimethyl methylglucuronoside (II), which was confirmed by preparing its amide (m.p. 185°) and comparing its physical properties with the amide of 2:3:4-trimethylglucuronic acid, reported by Smith and Cunnen (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1141). Fraction B on hydrolysis with aqueous 7% HCl and working out in the usual manner yielded two sugars. The non-acidic reducing sugar was found to be 2:3:4-trimethylgalactose from its physical constants as well as by preparing its anilide, which had m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen, 165° . The acidic sugar obtained was shown to be 2:3:4-trimethylglucuronic acid by preparing its crystalline 2:3:4-trimethylglucosaccharo-1:5-lactone-6-methyl ester (IX), m.p. and mixed m.p. with the authentic sample, $108-109^\circ$. The above results indicate that the aldobionic acid present in the modal gum has the structure (I).

The structure (I) assigned to the aldobionic acid was confirmed by preparing the amide (V) of its fully methylated derivative (III), m.p. 196° ; $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 24^\circ$ (c, 0.25% in water). The fully methylated derivative (III) as well as its amide (V) has been described in the literature (Smith and Jackson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 74) and the physical constants of both these derivatives agree well with the derivatives obtained in this work.

times with boiling alcohol till chromatographically free from sugars. The mixture of the barium salts was a pale yellow amorphous powder, yield 75 g., Ba, 13.3%; $[\alpha]_D^{20} \pm 0^\circ$.

Methylation of the Mixture of the Barium Salts of the Uronic Acids.—A portion of the barium salts (50 g.) was dissolved in water (150 c.c.), and acetone (100 c.c.) was added until a slight turbidity was observed. The solution was then treated with dimethyl sulphate (525 g.) and sodium hydroxide (950 c.c., 30%). Half of the reagents was added at the room temperature during 4 hours with vigorous stirring till the solution became non-reducing, while the remaining reagents were added at 70° during a period of 7 hours. The faintly alkaline solution was concentrated on a water-bath to a small bulk (250 c.c.), filtered to remove sodium sulphate, and remethylated by using dimethyl sulphate (500 g.) and sodium hydroxide (750 c.c., 30%). After three more methylations the mixture was cooled to 0° and was acidified with 25% H₂SO₄. Sodium sulphate, thus separated, was removed by filtration and the filtrate was extracted with chloroform (200 c.c. each time) three times. Sodium sulphate was also extracted with methyl alcohol, methyl alcohol was removed under reduced pressure and the solid obtained was extracted with chloroform. The extracts of chloroform were combined, washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent removed, when a mixture consisting of partially methylated uronic acids was obtained in the form of a syrup, yield 38 g., OMe, 35.66%.

The syrup (38 g.) was dissolved in methyl iodide (150 c.c.) and freshly prepared dry silver oxide (50 g.) was added to the refluxing solution with vigorous stirring during 8 hours. Silver oxide was then extracted with dry ether several times. On removal of ether and methyl iodide, the syrup obtained had OMe, 49.5%, yield 30 g. The syrup on remethylation by the above method did not show any rise in its methoxyl content. It was therefore distilled under reduced pressure and the following fractions were obtained. Fraction A: 14.2 g., b.p. 110°-115°/3 mm. Fraction B: 14.2 g., b.p. 268°-280°/3 mm. and the residue 13.0 g. The residue was not distillable and therefore was not examined.

Fraction A.—It is a yellow mobile liquid; η_D^{20} 1.44880; $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 31^\circ$ (c, 2.7% in water). (Found: C, 49.78; H, 7.4; OMe, 57.8. Calc. for C₁₁H₂₀O₇: C, 50.0; H, 7.57; OMe, 58.8 per cent).

The constants reported by Hirst and Jones (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1174) for methyl ester of 2:3:4-trimethyl methyl-*D*-glucuronoside (II) are: η_D^{20} 1.4471; $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 31^\circ$ (c, 0.7% in water). On treatment with ammonia at 0° for 48 hours, it furnished an amide (IV) which crystallised from ethanol-ether-petroleum ether (40°-60°), m.p. 185°; $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 140^\circ$ (c, 1% in water). (Found: N, 5.66; OMe, 48.9. Calc. for C₁₀H₁₉O₆N: N, 5.60; OMe, 49.80 per cent). Physical constants reported by Cunnen and Smith (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1141) for the amide of 2:3:4-trimethyl methyl-*D*-glucuronoside (IV) are: m.p. 185°; $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 137^\circ$ (c, 0.7% in water).

Fraction B.—It is a thick pale yellow liquid; η_D^{20} 1.4684; $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 24^\circ$ (c, 2% in water). (Found: C, 51.42; H, 7.90; OMe, 51.9; equiv., 464.1. Calc. for C₂₀H₃₆O₁₂: C, 51.29; H, 7.69; OMe, 51.0 per cent. Equiv., 468). The syrup on keeping for

several days at room temperature deposited white crystals of the methyl ester of hexamethyl-6-glucuronosido- β -methylgalactoside, which were isolated according to the method of Challinor, Hirst and Haworth (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 258), m.p. 81° ; OMe, 52.2%.

Hydrolysis of Methyl Heptamethylaldobionate (III).—Fraction B (6 g.) was dissolved in 7% aqueous HCl (100 c.c.) and was heated at 90° for 4 hours. The following changes in the optical rotation were observed: + $25^{\circ}.86$ (0 hr.), + 50° (1 hr.), + $64^{\circ}.66$ (2 hours), + $63^{\circ}.3$ (3 hours), + $65^{\circ}.1$ (4 hours, and remained constant further). Neutralisation of the hydrolysate with barium carbonate, followed by filtration and concentration under reduced pressure at 40° , furnished a pale yellow powder.

Isolation and Identification of 2:3:4-Trimethylgalactose (VI).—The brown-yellow powder was extracted with dry ether in a soxhlet. The extract on removal of the ether afforded a pale yellow reducing syrup, yield 2.2 g. η_{sp}^{25} 1.4734; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 83^{\circ}$ (c, 0.5% in water). (Found: C, 48.72; H, 7.18; OMe, 42.2. Calc. for $C_9H_{15}O_6$: C, 48.64; H, 8.11; OMe, 41.88 per cent). The sugar was identified as 2:3:4-trimethylgalactose by examining it on a paper chromatogram using butanol and petroleum ether (60° - 80°) (30:70 v/v) and running authentic sample of 2:3:4-trimethylgalactose side by side. The anilide of this sugar crystallised from ethyl alcohol, m.p. 165° . (Found: N, 4.87; OMe, 31.37. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{25}O_5N$: N, 4.70; OMe, 31.3 per cent). This did not depress the m.p. of the authentic specimen of the anilide of 2:3:4-trimethylgalactose, prepared by the method of McCreath and Smith (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 387).

Identification of 2:3:4-Trimethylglucuronic Acid.—The residue after ether extraction was extracted with dry chloroform from which the barium salt was precipitated by dry ether as a chromatographically pure, dry, brown powder, yield 3.8 g. [Found: OMe, 30.52; Ba, 22.2. Calc. for $(C_9H_{15}O_7)_2Ba$: OMe, 30.65; Ba, 22.57 per cent].

The barium salt (2 g.) was dissolved in water (15 c.c.) and bromine (3 c.c.) was added to it. The mixture was kept at room temperature for 4 days; bromine was then removed by aeration, and the solution was neutralised by barium carbonate, filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure to dryness. It was then boiled with methyl alcoholic hydrogen chloride (3%, 30 c.c.) for 6 hours. The hydrochloric acid was neutralised by silver carbonate and the filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure and was finally distilled. The syrupy liquid (1 g.) solidified, which was crystallised from ether-petroleum ether mixture, m.p. 108 - 109° ; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 90^{\circ}$ (c, 1% in water). This did not depress the m.p. of the authentic specimen of the lactone prepared by the method of Smith *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1734).

Preparation of the Amide of Hexamethyl 6-d-Glucuronosido-methylgalactopyranoside (V).—Fraction B (0.5 g.) was treated with anhydrous alcoholic ammonia for 48 hours at 0° . Removal of the solvent furnished white crystals which on recrystallisation from acetone-ether melted at 196° ; $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 24^{\circ}$ (c, 0.25% in water). (Found: C, 50.51; H, 7.8; OMe, 46.6. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{25}O_{11}N$: C, 50.34; H, 7.7; OMe, 47.9 per cent). Jackson and Smith (*loc. cit.*) reported the m.p. of the amide as 196° .